

TASK-BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING AND COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF TERTIARY LEARNERS: BASIS FOR AN INNOVATIVE COMMUNICATION ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Effective communication is essential in education as it influenced learners' academic engagement and learning opportunities (Widiastuti, et al., 2017). Hence, this study aimed to assess the communicative competence of tertiary students across four key areas: grammatical, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic. This study employed descriptive-correlational approach with a total of 150 participants who were selected through stratified random sampling. The data was taken from a six-part researcher-made questionnaire and was analyzed using applied statistical tools such as frequency counts and percentage, weighted mean and Pearson's *r* correlation test. The findings of the study revealed a moderate overall communicative competence among tertiary learners, with high levels observed in grammatical, sociolinguistic, and discourse competencies, and moderate level in strategic competence. Task-Based Language Teaching is perceived as highly effective in real-world communication development. However, Pearson's correlation test revealed no significant relationship between the perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching and grammatical, discourse, and strategic competencies, but a significant relationship with sociolinguistic competence; hereby implying that tertiary learners' who find TBLT more beneficial demonstrate a slightly better grasp of the social aspects of language use. Based on the findings: teachers are recommended to attend seminar-workshops on TBLT-informed pedagogies; curriculum experts are encouraged to periodically update the content of the existing syllabus on communication subjects and design it based on recent trajectories of English Language Teaching for the 21st century learning; and higher education institutions (HEIs) may adopt an innovative communication program tailored to enhance the communicative competence of the tertiary learners.

Keywords: *communicative competence, grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, strategic competence, Task-Based Language Teaching*

INTRODUCTION

Communication is vital for bridging cultural and societal gaps and serves as primary tool for growth and in facilitating meaningful engagement (Widiastuti et al., 2017). Within this context, English emerged as a reputable global lingua franca and is used by non-native speakers to navigate interaction with other non-native speakers (Maba, 2023). Consequently, this led to the formulation of rigid English language standards which neglected diverse variations, thus limiting effective communication (Abao, 2022).

On a related note, Smith and Jones (2023) reiterated that disproportionate attention given to the development of macro-skills such that writing and reading skills were overemphasized, fostered risk to oral communication development and created a gap in communicative competence. Significant issues were observed in both urban and rural academic settings that resulted in misunderstandings and ineffective interactions.

Learners frequently struggle with verbal expressions in English, experiencing humiliation and anxiety in group conversations (Sripradith, 2019). Mora et al. (2021) affirmed that major causes of communication difficulties include nervousness and timidity that is associate with the intricate structures of English and its components. A study about Indian students by Rahayu (2015) revealed lack of understanding on grammatical patterns and limited vocabulary on English language as major reasons behind communication anxieties of learners.

In a different view, Kanwit (2022) revealed that in so far as education focuses on intensifying grammar instruction in response to the deteriorating grammar proficiency of learners, the sociolinguistic aspect of communication posed other concerns in the communication realm. This aspect primarily concerns with adapting appropriate communication styles across social and cultural contexts.

Regarding communication skills, Alem (2020) highlighted that learners who are subjected to a foreign language instruction encounter difficulties in delivering persuasive information and negotiating meaning. This posed additional challenge for teachers to blend in varying strategies just to entertain language-driven barrier, and for students to explore on deviating from the focal language just to get ones' meaning across successfully. This scenario is also reflected in a typical Filipino classroom, despite English being a popular language in the Philippines.

Addressing these communication issues demands a comprehensive approach that integrates language learning with concrete opportunities for authentic communication and social interaction (Sayed, 2021). One emerging language approach pertinent to such is task-based language teaching. This approach provides a good alternative to traditional language pedagogy with its reiteration on real-world communication and learner-centered activities. It exposes learners to authentic tasks that permit application of language skills, hereby fostering deep understanding of language functions in diverse contexts, promoting progressive communication development (Skehan, 2021). Given the demands for effective communication skills,

Task-Based Language Teaching provides a systematic framework for developing language learnings and the language education in general.

As available literatures only ventured on how task-based language teaching influences the general aspect of communication, with the issues presented above, and the researcher's observation on prevalent communication issues manifested by the learners, the researcher decided to conduct the study titled Task-Based Language Teaching and Communicative Competence of Tertiary Learners: Basis for an Innovative Communication Enhancement Program.

The study sought to explore the communicative competence level of the learners in each major component, their perception of the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching in enhancing communication in real-world setting, the correlation of both variables. and to craft an innovative enhancement program to foster improvement in the communication capacities of tertiary learners. The insights acquired from this study served as valuable basis for educators, curriculum developers, and policy makers in their efforts to enhance communication competence of tertiary learners.

Research Questions

This study determined the extent of communicative competence of the tertiary learners of Christ the King College and their perception of the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching as basis for the development of an innovative communication enhancement program.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the tertiary learners in terms of program?
2. To what extent do tertiary learners demonstrate communicative competence in terms of:
 - 2.1 grammatical competence;
 - 2.2 sociolinguistic competence;
 - 2.3 discourse competence; and
 - 2.4 strategic competence?
3. How do tertiary learners perceive the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching in enhancing their ability to communicate in real-world situations?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the communicative competence of tertiary learners and their perception on the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)?
5. Based on the findings, what innovative enhancement program may be developed to enhance communicative competence of the tertiary learners?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, research locale, research participants, data gathering procedure, quantification of data, and statistical treatment that were applied in analyzing the gathered data.

Research Locale

The research was conducted at Christ the King College (CKC). This sectarian school is located at Mercado Avenue, Brgy. 23, Gingoog City, Misamis Oriental. Christ the King College was founded by Rev. Fr. Edward Wasil, SJ in 1947 with the name Christ the King Academy. The epoch of the Religious of the Virgin Mary (RVM) leadership began when Fr. William Adams, SSC decided to give both the ownership and administration of Christ the King College and its neighboring sister school Saint-Mary's Academy of Lunao to the RVM Congregation in 1961.

The school is offering complete K-12 program for the basic education and 8 programs for the higher education department and is catering not only to the people in Gingoog City, but also to the neighboring municipalities of Magsaysay, Medina, Talisayan, and Balingoan.

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study were the 150 first year tertiary students of Christ the King College (CKC) who are enrolled in the Purposive Communicative subject. These participants were taken from 7 programs namely; Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA), Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), Bachelor of Science in Social Work (BSSW), Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM), Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT), Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSCrim), and Teacher Education Program (TEP).

Sampling Design

There were 243 first year tertiary students of Christ the College, Gingoog City. To get a reasonable sample size for the study, Cochran's formula was used. Thus, only 150 first year tertiary students were involved in the study. To ensure that every program will be represented in the study, stratified sampling was applied.

In selecting the participants, the researcher employed simple lottery procedure. The names of the students were gathered from the office of the registrar and assigned a designated number for each. The numbers drawn corresponded to the names of the students. The students whose names were drawn were considered as participants of the study.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire which consisted of 6 parts. The first part was all about the demographic profile of the participants which contained their program. The second part pertained to the grammatical competence

of the participants, while the third part explored on the sociolinguistic competence of the learners. The fourth- and fifth-part surveyed the level of discourse and strategic competence of participants respectively. The sixth part delved on the perception of the respondents regarding Task-Based Language Teaching and its impact to real-life communication. Before formulating the research questionnaire, the researcher first reviewed different researches to ascertain that the questions to be formulated are appropriate and relevant.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the research questionnaire, the researcher submitted a copy of the self-made questionnaire to the three panel of experts whose expertise are relevant to English language teaching. After consolidating feedbacks and points of improvement from the experts, the researcher revised the questionnaire. It was then tried out to 40 students. The data were tallied and analyzed by a statistician for its reliability coefficient. The result of the reliability test showed that the research instrument is reliable with a Cronbach's Alpha Value of 0.837.

Scoring and Quantification

The proficiency level of the participants among four major components of communicative competence as well as the perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching in enhancing their ability to communicate in real-world situations was quantified using the Likert scale as presented below:

Response	Verbal Description	Range	Interpretation/ Remark
5	Strongly Agree	4.50-5.00	Very High
4	Agree	3.50-4.49	High
3	Neutral	2.50-3.49	Moderate
2	Disagree	1.50-2.49	Low
1	Strongly Disagree	1.00-1.49	Very Low

Data-gathering Procedure

To gather the data, the study made use of the self-made questionnaire and employed the following strategies:

Pre-data Gathering Stage. Before the conduct of the study, the researcher secured a letter of permission. It was signed and granted by the Dean of College and School President of Christ the King College. After that, the said letter with the specific schedule for the conveying of the respondents was presented to the program coordinators of the seven programs involved.

Actual Data-gathering Stage. The researcher personally administered the research instrument. Before the administration, the researcher conducted a brief orientation with the participants on the nature of the study and assured them that the data they provided would be treated with the utmost confidentiality. The research also navigated the items in each part of the questionnaire for ease of understanding on the respondents' end. After the administration, the researcher then collected back the questionnaires that the participants answered.

Organization Phase. After the successful retrieval of the research instrument, students' responses were organized using an excel form document where 5 sheets were used to provide proper distinction of the major aspects of the questionnaire.

Data Interpretation Phase. After organizing students' responses, the data were submitted to a statistician for data analysis.

Statistical Treatment

To analyze the data gathered, the study made use of the following statistical tools:

Frequency Counts and Percentages. These were used to determine the demographic profile of the participants.

Mean. This was employed to determine the level of agreement or disagreement of the participants on the indicators pertaining to the four major components of communicative competence and the perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching in enhancing communication in real-world settings.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient. This was utilized to determine whether a significant relationship between the communicative competence of participants and their perception on the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT).

RESULTS

Problem 1. Demographic Profile of the Participants

Table 1 presents the frequency and percent of the participants program profile distribution.

Table 1.

Program Profile Distribution (%) of the Participants.

Program Distribution	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Social Work	30	20.0	20.0	20.0
Accountancy	23	15.3	15.3	35.3
Hospitality and Management	20	13.3	13.3	48.7
Information and Technology	20	13.3	13.3	61.3
Teacher Education	20	13.3	13.3	75.7
Criminal Justice	20	13.3	13.3	88.7
Business Administration	17	11.3	11.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 shows that 20.0% of the participants are from the Social Work Program. It is followed by the Accountancy program which is 15.3%. It can also be noted that the Criminal Justice, Hospitality and Management, Information and Technology as well as the Teacher Education program respectively constituted 13.3% of the population while only 11.3% are from the Business Administration. This suggests that a significant

portion of participants were from the Social Work program, supporting the assertion made by Mckenzie (2022) that enrollment in the aforementioned program is on the rise and is linked to a greater understanding of social justice issues and a desire to effect change. Price and Artaraz (2013) supported this claim with their study that revealed that the Social Work program provided a purposive tool to counter-refute and resist the present experiences of imperialism such as the hierarchical biases in certain professions within the Philippine domain.

Problem 2. Extent of Communicative Competence of the Tertiary Learners

Table 2 presents the mean distribution of the extent of grammatical competence of the tertiary learners

Based on the table, it can be noted that 2nd indicator, which states that learners ensure subject-verb agreement in their writing, even in complex sentences, garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.54 which can be interpreted as very high. This suggests that students possess a deep comprehension of the rules governing subject-verb agreement. When creating difficult sentence constructions, they are quite skilled at making sure that verbs agree with their corresponding subjects.

Marjokorpi (2023) supported this finding with a study that looked at college and high school students' writing examples. Accordingly, strong grammar scores were found to be significantly correlated with the capacity to uphold subject-verb agreement, even in complex phrases.

It is crucial to remember, though, that this finding contradicts research by Rifki et al., (2019) which claimed that Junior High School learners have difficulty in terms of connecting subjects and verbs correctly. Housen and Simoens (2018) revealed that younger generations' formal writing skills may suffer from their frequent usage of subject-verb agreement-laxing social media and texting language.

On the other hand, 4th indicator, which states that learners incorporated transitional words and phrases to connect ideas smoothly within and across sentences in their writing got the lowest weighted mean of 2.34 interpreted as low. This implies that the learners are having trouble using transitional words and phrases in their writing to effectively connect ideas within and between sentences. This is troubling since writing that is coherent and clear requires the skillful application of transitions. Johnson et al. (2019), found that one frequent obstacle impeding students' ability to produce the more cohesive and sophisticated writing anticipated at higher educational levels was their inability to use transitional devices fluently.

The overall weighted mean of the extent of the students' demonstration of grammatical competence is 3.55 which can be interpreted as high. This means that relative to their communicative competence, the learners manifest a high level of grammatical competence. They create clear, well-written sentences by exhibiting a thorough comprehension of grammatical rules. This entails understanding of word order, common grammatical patterns, and the fundamental sentence elements (subject, verb, and object). Good grammar allows one to create clear messages, which is essential for communicating effectively.

Table 2.*Mean Distribution of the Extent of Grammatical Competence of the Tertiary Learners*

Grammatical Competence		Proficiency Level		
	Indicators	Mean	Description	Interpretation
1	I use correct verb tenses to convey time accurately in my writing.	4.22	Agree	High
2	I ensure subject-verb agreement in my writing, even in complex sentences.	4.54	Strongly Agree	Very High
3	I employ variety of sentence structures (e.g., simple, compound, complex) to communicate my ideas clearly.	3.50	Agree	High
4	I incorporate transitional words and phrases to connect ideas smoothly within and across sentences in my writing.	2.34	Disagree	Low
5	I utilize pronouns to avoid confusion and maintain clarity in my writing.	3.89	Agree	High
6	I use modifiers (e.g., adjectives and adverbs) to add details and enhance the meaning of my writing.	4.28	Agree	High
7	I identify and correct grammatical errors in my own writing and speech.	3.42	Neutral	Moderate
8	I adapt my grammar use to different writing situations to ensure clear communication.	3.43	Neutral	Moderate
9	I use grammatical structures to express complex ideas clearly in both written and spoken communication.	2.44	Disagree	Low
10	I use punctuation marks correctly to enhance clarity and avoid confusion in my writing.	3.52	Agree	High
Overall Weighted Mean		3.55	Agree	High

Range of means: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Neutral; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree

This finding aligns with Wolfe and Hood (2020) who found that students' writing accuracy and general language ability significantly improved after receiving targeted grammar training. Myhill et al. (2020) highlighted that students' reading comprehension abilities can be improved by having a solid foundation in grammar, which enables them to comprehend the organization and meaning of written content. These studies demonstrate the beneficial effects of grammatical proficiency on a range of language development domains.

However, this finding contradicts Nayan (2009) as cited by Sioco and De Vera (2018) which claimed that Filipino learners are not adept in applying grammar rules of English language despite it being taught at their very young age. This was made apparent by the observed difficulties and struggles of learners not only in Junior High School but also in higher levels when engaged to classroom activities that necessitates the application of the introduced grammar rules.

From a theoretical perspective, this result implies that students are growing in their comprehension of Chomsky's definition of linguistic competence (Abdulrahman & Abu-Ayyash, 2019) The internalized knowledge of language structure and rules is

referred to as linguistic competence. A high degree of grammatical competence shows that students have the mental grammar necessary to construct and understand sentences in their target language. This skill is an essential part of communicative competence, which includes knowing how to use language correctly in many social and communication contexts.

Table 3.

Mean distribution of the extent of sociolinguistic competence of the tertiary learners

Sociolinguistic Competence		Proficiency Level		
	Indicators	Mean	Description	Interpretation
1	I tailor my communication style (e.g., word choice, tone, formality) to match different social settings.	3.62	Agree	High
2	I demonstrate awareness of cultural norms in language use (e.g., greetings and politeness markers).	3.38	Neutral	Moderate
3	I use appropriate titles (e.g., Mr. or Ms.) and language in formal and informal settings.	4.20	Agree	High
4	I respect different ways people speak like accents and dialects.	3.55	Agree	High
5	I use appropriate language based on factors such as age, gender, ethnicity, and social identity.	3.66	Agree	High
6	I adapt my communication style to meet the needs of my audience.	4.08	Agree	High
7	I use respectful language that aligns with the expectations of different roles, relationships, and settings.	4.31	Agree	High
8	I use strategies to repair problems in conversations.	4.01	Agree	High
9	I respond appropriately to implied meanings and nonverbal cues within different social interactions.	2.43	Disagree	Low
10	I resolve issues in intercultural communication by seeking clarification and demonstrating cultural sensitivity.	4.47	Agree	High
Overall Weighted Mean		3.77	Agree	High

Range of means: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Neutral; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree

Table 3 shows the mean distribution of the extent of tertiary learners' sociolinguistic competence.

The highest-ranked value, with a mean score of 4.47 is the 10th indicator which states that participants showed cultural sensitivity and asked for clarification when needed to effectively address problems in cross-cultural communication. This suggests a high level of competence and adaptability in adjusting to various cultural contexts. It implies that tertiary learners are good at appreciating and understanding cultural differences, which makes their cross-cultural interactions easier. Being able to communicate effectively across cultural boundaries is crucial in the globally connected

world of today, when it is becoming more and more frequent to contact with people from different origins. This result is consistent with earlier studies on intercultural communication competency, which highlight the value of cultural sensitivity and flexibility in promoting successful cross-cultural exchanges as well as overcoming cultural barriers triggered by diversity of people in the workplace. Furthermore, it supports research results that demonstrate the beneficial effects of cultural competency training programs on people's capacity to deal with the difficulties of cross-cultural communication (Deardorff, 2009).

On the other hand, the one with the lowest mean score of 2.43 is the 9th indicator which states that learners responded appropriately to implied meanings and nonverbal cues within different social interactions. This indicates disagreement and suggesting a low level of competence in this aspect. This finding emphasizes how difficult it can be for learners to correctly decipher nonverbal clues and implicit information during social encounters. Smith et al. (2021) showed that misinterpreting nonverbal cues can cause misunderstandings and interpersonal problems, emphasizing the significance of being skilled at deciphering nonverbal communication. Targeted interventions aiming at increasing awareness and understanding of nonverbal communication signals may be beneficial for individuals who have difficulty reacting to suggested meanings and nonverbal cues. This will ultimately improve the interpersonal efficacy of these individuals in social interactions.

The low score on this item also suggests areas where the learners may improve their communication skills. Body language, tone of voice, and facial expressions are examples of nonverbal cues that are used in effective communication in addition to spoken language. To increase their capacity to correctly interpret implicit signals, those who find it difficult to react to suggested meanings and nonverbal cues could find it helpful to enroll in communication skills training programs or ask peers and mentors for feedback.

The overall weighted mean score of 3.77 indicates a high level of agreement among respondents regarding their communication behaviors across the assessed indicators of sociolinguistic competence. This implies that tertiary learners generally believe they are skilled communicators who can successfully navigate a range of social and cultural circumstances. This result is consistent with the study by Grady, Kang, and Hyun (2016), which highlights how important good communication is to creating long-lasting organizations, but is contrary to Valda (2011) which asserted that speakers who are fluent in grammar are unable to produce culturally and socially appropriate language.

Table 4.

Mean distribution of the extent of discourse competence of the tertiary learners

Discourse Competence		Proficiency Level		
	Indicators	Mean	Description	Interpretation
1	I organize my ideas in a logical sequence that makes my communication easy to follow.	4.01	Agree	High

2	I use connecting words and phrases (e.g., 'however', 'because', 'firstly') to clearly show the relationships between my ideas.	3.38	Neutral	Moderate
3	I utilize pronouns, repetition, and transitions to create a smooth flow of ideas, both in writing and speaking.	4.20	Agree	High
4	I change how I structure my sentences and paragraphs to fit different purposes (e.g., writing an email vs. giving a speech).	2.45	Disagree	Low
5	I break complex information into smaller, easier-to-understand parts.	3.66	Agree	High
6	I manage conversations by taking turns, adjusting my pace, and responding thoughtfully to others.	2.48	Disagree	Low
7	I use examples and vivid descriptions to clarify my ideas and make my communication more engaging.	4.31	Agree	High
8	I ask clarifying questions and rephrase ideas to make sure I understand extended conversations.	3.62	Agree	High
9	I adjust the formality of my language to suit different communicative situations.	2.43	Disagree	Low
10	I employ communication techniques like questioning, summarizing, and providing examples to achieve specific goals in a conversation.	4.47	Agree	High
Overall Weighted Mean		3.50	Agree	High

Range of means: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Neutral; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree

Table 4 shows the mean distribution of the extent of tertiary learners' discourse competence.

The 10th indicator, which states that learners employed communication techniques like questioning, summarizing, and providing examples to achieve specific goals in a conversation, received the highest mean score of 4.47, indicating strong agreement among respondents and is interpreted as high. This suggests a high level of proficiency in employing tactics of strategic communication to accomplish goals.

Gudykunst and Ting-Toomey (2020), claimed that effective interpersonal interactions require the use of certain strategic communication approaches. Utilizing strategic communication behaviors to achieve desired outcomes, it is implied by the high degree of agreement that respondents appreciate the strategic importance of methods like summarizing and questioning in promoting comprehension, resolving disagreements, and creating rapport.

Meanwhile, the 9th indicator, which states that learners adjusted the formality of their language to suit different communicative situations received the lowest mean score of 2.43. This is interpreted as low and projects disagreement among respondents. This indicates that opinions on how important it is to modify language formality in different communicative circumstances are divided.

Ardi et al. (2018) highlighted that people modify the formality of their language according to the social setting in order to preserve pleasant social relationships. This emphasizes the importance of politeness techniques in communication. Disagreement with this value might point to a need for better comprehension of and application of proper linguistic formality in communication.

The overall weighted mean score of 3.50, which is interpreted as high, suggests a generally high level of agreement among participants regarding their communication behaviors across the assessed dimensions of discourse competence. This indicates that, on average, learners perceive themselves as skilled communicators who can handle a variety of social and communication situations with ease.

This result is consistent with Kang, et al., (2016), which highlighted how important good communication is to creating long-lasting organizations. The high degree of agreement indicates that respondents prioritize involvement, and clarity in their interactions. This might have tolerance for a variety of situations, such as interpersonal relationships, professional communication, and education.

On the other hand, this finding is incongruent to the study of Agustin et al., (2022) which highlighted that one major concern faced by learners in crafting written discourse is the seamless connection or transition of one idea to another. This is highly observed especially in classroom writing activities that would involve lengthy outputs such as essays and position papers.

Table 5 shows the mean distribution of the extent of tertiary learners' strategic competence.

Among all the items, the 10th indicator which pertained to the reflective practice of assessing communication effectiveness and adjusting for future interactions got the highest mean at 3.57. This finding is interpreted as high and suggests that a significant portion of tertiary students recognize that self-reflection is crucial to improving their communication abilities. Johnson et al. (2019) found that enhanced self-awareness, critical thinking, and skill development are associated with reflective practices in communication education. As a result, students who participate in reflective practices are probably going to show consistent growth in their communication skills, which will allow them to successfully adjust to various situations and obstacles.

Table 5.

Mean distribution of the extent of the strategic competence of the tertiary learners

Strategic Competence		Proficiency Level		
	Indicators	Mean	Description	Interpretation
1	I define my communication goals clearly before starting a conversation or interaction.	3.32	Neutral	Moderate
2	I identify potential misunderstanding and develop strategies (e.g., clarifying questions, rephrasing, finding common ground) to address them.	2.38	Disagree	Low

3	I choose the most appropriate communication channels based on the situation and audience.	3.40	Neutral	Moderate
4	I use nonverbal cues (e.g., eye contact, posture, gestures) intentionally to support my message.	3.55	Agree	High
5	I monitor how the communication is progressing and adjust my approach if needed.	2.46	Disagree	Low
6	I use persuasive language techniques (e.g., appeals to logic or emotion) to influence others.	3.08	Neutral	Moderate
7	I manage conflict by communicating clearly, actively listening, and focusing on finding solutions.	3.21	Neutral	Moderate
8	I use communication techniques to build trust and rapport with others.	2.21	Disagree	Low
9	I communicate assertively to express my needs and advocate for myself and others	2.43	Disagree	Low
10	I reflect on the effectiveness of my communication and adjust for future interactions.	3.57	Agree	High
Overall Weighted Mean		2.96	Neutral	Moderate

Range of means: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Neutral; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree

On the other hand, the 8th indicator, which corresponds to using communication techniques to build trust and rapport with others has the lowest value of 2.21 and is interpreted as low. This suggests that a significant fraction of college students reject the idea of using communication techniques to build rapport and trust. Nonetheless, Chen and Peng (2018) highlighted how important rapport and trust are to the development of effective interpersonal interactions and teamwork. Consequently, resolving this disparity by incorporating techniques for fostering trust into communication education curricula may improve students' capacity for developing relationships and interpersonal competences.

Overall, the mean distribution of the extent of strategic competence among tertiary learners indicates a neutral stance at 2.96, suggesting a moderate level of agreement across the surveyed indicators. This implies that although there is always space for development, many students have a solid understanding of strategic communication techniques. Educational institutions should think about implementing focused interventions and opportunities for experiential learning to enhance students' strategic competence and equip them for the intricate communication requirements of both professional and academic settings.

Table 6 shows the summary of the level of communicative competence of tertiary learners across four major components.

Table 6.*Summary of the Level of Communicative Competence of Tertiary Learners*

Communicative Competence Component	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Grammatical Competence	3.55	High	2 nd
Sociolinguistic Competence	3.77	High	1 st
Discourse Competence	3.50	High	3 rd
Strategic Competence	2.96	Neutral	4 th
Overall Weighted Mean	3.44	Neutral	

Range of means: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Neutral; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree

Based on the data presented, the communicative competence levels of tertiary learners slightly vary across various domains. Sociolinguistic competence emerges as the highest-rated aspect among the learners, with a mean score of 3.77, indicating a high level of proficiency in understanding and appropriately using language in social contexts. This is consistent with Brown (2019), which highlighted the role that sociolinguistic ability plays in enabling social engagement and successful communication. A strong set of sociolinguistic skills helps students effectively navigate a variety of social and cultural contexts, which improves their general efficacy in communication as well as their intercultural competence.

Grammatical proficiency is a close second, coming in with a mean score of 3.56, which is considered high. This demonstrates the students' solid command of grammatical structures and rules, which are necessary for precise and understandable communication. Barraquio, (2015), reiterated that mastery of grammar paves the way for efficient communication across a variety of disciplines and emphasizes the fundamental role that grammatical competence plays in language acquisition and competency development. However, this contradicts the study of Rahayu, (2015) which revealed that learners lack of understanding of major grammatical patterns is a significant problem for individuals who are using English as a foreign language.

Discourse competence ranks third in the summary, with a mean score of 3.50, indicating a high level of proficiency in organizing and structuring extended stretches of discourse. Discourse competence includes the capacity to contribute to meaningful communication encounters by organizing ideas coherently, speaking coherently, and maintaining coherence. Celce-Murcia and Olshtain (2022), discourse competency has a crucial role in enabling effective communication and is significant in social, professional, and academic contexts. Learners can more effectively communicate complicated concepts and actively engage in discourse communities by becoming proficient in discourse tactics and discourse markers.

However, despite the high rating in sociolinguistic competence, it is noteworthy that strategic competence, with a mean score of 2.96, is rated lowest comparatively, positioning it as the least area of competence among the learners. This indicates a moderate level of agreement regarding the extent of strategic competence, suggesting room for improvement in areas such as goal setting, conflict management, and persuasive communication strategies.

Dawit (2020) stressed the critical role that strategic competency plays in effective communication, highlighting its importance in accomplishing communication objectives and skillfully handling interpersonal dynamics. Thus, learners' overall communicative competence and preparedness for academic and professional efforts could be improved by addressing strategic competency gaps through focused interventions and practical learning opportunities.

The overall weighted mean of 3.44 reflects a neutral stance on the communicative competence of tertiary learners, indicating a moderate level of agreement across the evaluated domains. This suggests that while learners exhibit strengths in certain areas such as sociolinguistic and grammatical competence, there are areas for growth and development, particularly in strategic competence.

It is imperative that these gaps in capability be filled in order to guarantee that students have the abilities needed to succeed in a variety of communication situations. Through the incorporation of communicative skill development into curriculum design and pedagogical approaches, educational institutions can assume a vital role in this process.

In order to equip students to become proficient communicators who can handle the challenges of interpersonal and cross-cultural communication, educators should provide a communicative environment that promotes active involvement, critical thinking, and skill application. Furthermore, the integration of reflective practices and feedback mechanisms can promote continuous self-evaluation and enhancement, ultimately aiding in the comprehensive advancement of communicative competence among tertiary students.

Problem 3. Perceived Effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching

Table 7 shows the mean distribution of the participants' perception on the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching in enhancing ability to communicate in real-world situations.

The data presented shows the perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) in enhancing the participants' abilities to communicate in real-world situations.

Among all the statements, the 3rd indicator, attributed to the statement, TBLT taught me how to use nonverbal communication (e.g., eye contact and gestures) effectively has highest mean value of 3.71, and interpreted as high.

Table 7.

Mean distribution of the participants' perception on the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching in enhancing ability to communicate in real-world situations

Task-Based Language Teaching Effectiveness		Effectiveness Level		
	Indicators	Mean	Description	Interpretation
1	TBLT improved my ability to express my ideas clearly in various real-life situations.	3.53	Agree	High

2	TBLT helped me become a better listener, paying attention to both verbal and nonverbal cues.	3.70	Agree	High
3	TBLT taught me how to use nonverbal communication (e.g., eye contact and gestures) effectively.	3.71	Agree	High
4	TBLT helped me develop strategies for respectfully handling disagreements in real-world situations.	3.59	Agree	High
5	TBLT improved my ability to adjust my communication style to suit different social, cultural, and professional settings.	3.63	Agree	High
6	TBLT made me more aware of how cultural differences influence communication styles.	3.52	Agree	High
7	TBLT helped me better understand the emotions and perspectives of others.	3.53	Agree	High
8	TBLT helped me use critical thinking and problem-solving skills to overcome communication challenges.	3.40	Neutral	Moderate
9	TBLT improved my ability to negotiate effectively and find solutions to conflicts.	3.42	Neutral	Moderate
10	TBLT gave me opportunities to practice expressing myself respectfully, which boosted my communication confidence.	3.54	Agree	High
Overall Weighted Mean		3.56	Agree	High

Range of means: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Neutral; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree

The significance of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) in addressing both verbal and non-verbal communication is emphasized by this statement. The implications of these findings suggest that Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) interventions offer learners comprehensive communication qualities that are crucial for effective interaction in authentic settings, surpassing just linguistic abilities. The significance of nonverbal cues in interpersonal interactions for the purposes of expressing meaning and establishing rapport has been supported by various studies (Knapp & Hall, 2014).

On the other hand, the 8th indicator, which states that TBLT helped learners used critical thinking and problem-solving skills to overcome communication challenges, got the lowest mean value of 3.40 moderate. Although not as highly supported as previous assertions, this finding nonetheless indicates a moderate degree of consensus regarding the potential of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) in fostering critical thinking within communication settings. This highlights the necessity for additional investigation and enhancement of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) methodologies in order to effectively incorporate critical thinking elements into language acquisition endeavors.

The overall mean value of 3.56, interpreted as high, reflects participants' general agreement on the effectiveness of TBLT in enhancing their ability to communicate in real-world situations. The weighted mean reflects a high assessment of the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) in different communication skills and circumstances, highlighting its significance in the field of language education. This highlights the importance of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) in enhancing learners' ability to communicate effectively and

equipping them for practical language usage outside of the classroom. The results and explanations align with previous research on Task-Based Language Teaching, which highlights its significance in enhancing communicative proficiency and practical language application (Smith, 2018). It further emphasized the necessity of incorporating TBLT methods into language instruction programs to more effectively equip learners for communication in various situations.

In contrast, Task-Based Language Teaching posed a risk for learners to attain fluency at the expense of accuracy (Tan, 2016). While this approach can indeed foster fluency by encouraging learners to communicate freely and naturally, it may sometimes neglect the finer points of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. In traditional language teaching approaches, accuracy often takes precedence, with a focus on drilling grammar rules and vocabulary memorization. However, this can sometimes hinder fluency development as learners may become overly concerned with producing perfect sentences rather than expressing themselves spontaneously (Yuko, 2011).

Therefore, while TBLT can be an effective approach for developing fluency, it's essential to balance it with activities that focus on accuracy to ensure that learners develop a well-rounded proficiency in the language. By integrating tasks that target both fluency and accuracy, teachers can create a more comprehensive language learning experience that prepares learners to communicate effectively in real-life situations.

Problem 4. Significant Relationship Between the Communicative Competence of Participants and the Perceived Effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)

Table 8 shows the significant relationship between grammatical competence of the participants and the perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT).

The findings revealed a correlation value at $r = 0.379$ between students' grammatical competence and their perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). This suggests that learners with moderate grammatical foundation tend to have a favorable perception of TBLT. However, it's important to note that this correlation is not statistically significant at $p = 0.279$.

Table 8.
Significant relationship between grammatical competence and the extent of perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Grammatical Competence	Extent of Perceived Effectiveness of TBLT	0.379	0.279	Moderate and positive	Not Significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Pearson's r correlation test; -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

While a moderate correlation hints at a connection, the lack of statistical significance emphasizes that grammatical proficiency is probably just one of the elements that impact students' opinions of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). Research substantiates this concept; studies demonstrate that the design of tasks itself is crucial for the success of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) (Viera, 2017). The presence of tasks that are pertinent, captivating, and suitably demanding contributes to heightened student motivation and a more favorable overall educational encounter. Furthermore, the teacher's responsibility in delivering explicit instructions, promoting engagement, and providing valuable feedback can significantly influence students' perception of the efficacy of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) (Nunan, 2004).

Table 9 shows the significant relationship between sociolinguistic competence of the participants and the perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT).

Table 9.

Significant relationship between sociolinguistic competence and the extent of perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Sociolinguistic Competence	Extent of Perceived Effectiveness of TBLT	0.253	0.039*	Weak and positive	Significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Pearson's r correlation test; -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

As shown in table 10, a weak positive correlation at $r = 0.253$ exists between learners' perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and their sociolinguistic competence. This suggests a slight tendency for students who find TBLT more beneficial to also demonstrate a slightly better grasp of the social aspects of language use which is deemed as core of sociolinguistic competence. Importantly, this correlation is statistically significant at $p = 0.039$.

Notwithstanding the statistical significance, this finding underscores the notion that sociolinguistic skill is likely to have a limited impact on students' evaluations of the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). Scholarly investigations underscore the significance of additional variables, such as the level of student engagement in Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), the extent to which these tasks align with students' interests, and the degree of assistance and facilitation offered by the instructor (Smith, 2018).

There is a potential correlation between students who possess a pre-existing sensitivity to the communicative and social dimensions of language and their increased enjoyment of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), as well as their heightened sociolinguistic competence. Moreover, the manner in which sociolinguistic competence is assessed may impact the outcomes; it is possible that a more robust

correlation exists with particular social abilities that are directly honed through the TBLT exercises.

Teachers utilizing Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) should not overlook the cultivation of sociolinguistic proficiency. Creating tasks that need the use of language in various social contexts and for varied objectives can improve both sociolinguistic abilities and the overall effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) (Littlewood, 2014).

Additional research should investigate how the specific structure of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) activities, in conjunction with instructor assistance, can promote the growth of students' sociolinguistic proficiency in addition to their communicative language abilities.

Table 10 shows the significant relationship between discourse competence of the participants and the perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT).

Table 10.

Significant relationship between discourse competence and the extent of perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Discourse Competence	Extent of Perceived Effectiveness of TBLT	0.174	0.629	Weak and positive	Not significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Pearson's r correlation test; -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

As revealed in the data, a correlation value with $r = 0.174$ exists between learners' perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and their discourse competence. This observation implies that students who perceive Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) as more advantageous tend to have somewhat higher proficiency in comprehending and generating coherent written and spoken language. Nevertheless, the absence of statistical significance at $p = 0.629$ suggests that the observed association may be attributable to random variation, implying that the impact of discourse competency on students' perception of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) may not be substantial.

This finding indicates that although proficiency in discourse is significant, it may not be the main factor influencing students' favorable attitudes towards Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). Research emphasizes that elements such as captivating task structure, student drive, and proficient teacher assistance have a greater impact on the perceived achievement of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) implementation (Ellis, 2003; Nunan, 2004).

Although the statistical correlation is limited, the ability to engage in effective conversation is nonetheless a valuable result of good language acquisition. Educators

should persist in explicitly incorporating the instruction of speech characteristics within a Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) framework. Additional investigation is required to examine how the structure of certain Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) tasks can enhance the cultivation of discourse competence in conjunction with other communicative language abilities.

Table 11 shows the significant relationship between strategic competence of the participants and the perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT).

Table 11.

Significant relationship between strategic competence and the extent of perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Strategic Competence	Extent of Perceived Effectiveness of TBLT	0.254	0.478	Weak and positive	Not significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Pearson's r correlation test; -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

As presented in table 11, a correlation value of $r = 0.254$ suggests a possible relationship between students' perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and their strategic competence. Those who find TBLT more beneficial may exhibit slightly stronger skills in using language resourcefully to overcome communication challenges. However, this relationship is not statistically significant at $p = 0.478$.

This finding suggests that although strategic competency may play a role in fostering a favorable image of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), it is unlikely to be the predominant determinant shaping students' perspectives. The efficacy of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is contingent upon the presence of meticulously crafted tasks that are both captivating and significant, in conjunction with a nurturing classroom atmosphere that fosters student motivation and active engagement (Sholeh, 2020).

However, one must bear in mind that correlation does not imply causation. It is possible that students who possess inherent abilities in effectively handling communication failures and devising alternate methods to convey their intended message are more inclined to derive satisfaction from Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and exhibit enhanced strategic competence. Moreover, the precise strategic abilities evaluated in the study can influence the outcomes.

Despite the limited statistical correlation, strategic competence continues to be an essential component of communication proficiency. Educators utilizing Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) should design instructional activities that explicitly necessitate learners to engage in the application of diverse strategic abilities, such as circumlocution (the process of speaking around unfamiliar vocabulary), seeking

clarification, or leveraging gestures and nonverbal indicators. Further investigation is required to examine the optimal ways in which Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) design and implementation might effectively facilitate the acquisition of strategic competence in students, in conjunction with other facets of language acquisition.

Problem 5. Proposed Innovative Communication Enhancement Program

The findings of the study showed that communicative competence of the tertiary learners is in a neutral stance or in a moderate level. While the data revealed that the tertiary learners have scored high on grammatical, sociolinguistic, and discourse competence, they have scored moderately neutral on strategic competence. Meanwhile, the learners' perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching was high, establishing the approach capacity to impact communication in real-world set up. As such, to enhance the communicative competence of the learners across all 4 major component competence with special attention to strategic competence, the researcher enclosed herewith the proposed innovative enhancement program; **NONCHALANT: Nurturing Optimal Networking for Communication Habits and Language Techniques.**

- I. **Program Title:** NONCHALANT: Nurturing Optimal Networking for Communication Habits and Linguistic Techniques
- II. **Program Description:** This intervention program is designed by the researcher based on the findings of the study, "Task-Based Language Teaching and Communicative Competence of Tertiary Learners: Basis for an Innovative Communication Enhancement Program
- III. **Program Overview:** The core principle underlying the NONCHALANT program is the cultivation of a state of calmness and composure. Based on the contextual definition of "nonchalant," this program provides participants with reassurance that within the domain of communication, anxiety could be handled in a least disadvantage way. It advocates for the notion that there are solutions available for every communication obstacle. By providing this basis, NONCHALANT enables participants to address communication problems with assurance, recognizing that solutions are easily accessible. The curriculum is designed to improve communication skills, promote effective networking, and refine language strategies. Participants will acquire communicative competence in multiple domains, such as grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, and strategic competence, through a combination of interactive workshops, experiential learning activities, and customized coaching. Participants' growth and progress will be ensured through the use of authentic and performance-based assessments.

Through this program, participants embark on a transformative journey towards mastering communication habits and linguistic techniques with a fearless and assured mindset.

IV. Program Objectives:

- Enhance grammatical competence to improve clarity and precision in communication.

- Develop sociolinguistic competence for effective communication in diverse social contexts.
- Cultivate discourse competence to convey ideas cohesively and persuasively.
- Foster strategic competence to adapt communication strategies to achieve specific goals.

V. **Target Audience:** 1st Year Tertiary Learners of Christ the King College-Gingoog City.

VI. **Duration:** 7 weeks (1 session per week)

VII. **Scheme Implementation:**

The program is divided into three (3) stages. Phase I will involve the Pre-Intervention Phase wherein the proposed communication enhancement program will be endorsed to the school administrators for approval and implementation. Phase 2 is the intervention phase wherein the enhancement program will be implemented. Phase 3 is the Post intervention wherein the administrators and teachers' make post-program evaluation of the intervention's effectiveness.

VIII. **Key Components:**

1. In-depth Exploration of Communication Domains: Workshops will be explored into the diagnosed issues in communication domains, including grammatical, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic competencies, providing participants with a comprehensive understanding.

2. Interactive Workshops and Practical Exercises: Through interactive sessions and practical exercises, participants will be engaged in hands-on learning to reinforce concepts and develop practical skills effectively.

3. Expert-led Discussions and Q&A Sessions: Participants will have the chance to enhance their comprehension and acquire valuable knowledge from seasoned professionals through expert-led conversations and question-and-answer sessions.

4. Real-world Application and Skill Practice: Engaging in experiential activities, such as role-playing scenarios and participating in group projects, participants will be given the chance to use recently gained skills within genuine circumstances.

5. Observational Exercises: Observational exercises enable learners to witness the practical application of successful communication, so promoting introspection and enhancing their understanding.

IX. **Topic and Activities Composition:**

Module 1: Mastering Transitional Flow in Writing

Participants will discover techniques for developing smooth and coherent connections between ideas in writing. The workshops primarily center around the identification and integration of transitional words and phrases inside and across sentences. The participants in the writing workshop engage in the practice of integrating transitional cues in order to improve coherence.

Module 2: Enhancing Interpretation of Nonverbal Cues

This module focuses on grasping the function of nonverbal signs in social interactions. Insights into the interpretation of suggested meanings and nonverbal clues are facilitated through workshops, while participants' capacity to respond effectively is enhanced through role-playing scenarios.

Module 3: Adapting Language Formality for Effective Communication

Participants get the ability to adapt the level of formality in language according to the specific context. The workshops delve into the intricacies of language register and offer practical exercises for practice. Participants enhance their proficiency in adjusting linguistic formality through the utilization of communication context simulations.

Module 4: Building Trust and Rapport through Effective Communication

This module emphasizes effective communication strategies to build trust and establish rapport. Workshops aim to identify and address obstacles to trust, while trust-building exercises foster collaboration and rapport among participants.

Module 5: Addressing Misunderstandings and Assertive Communication

This module focuses on developing strong communication skills and effectively resolving misunderstandings. Participants will gain valuable skills in assertive communication through engaging in role-play scenarios and participating in assertiveness training.

Figure 3: Phases of the Proposed Innovative Communication Enhancement Program

Phase I. Pre-Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of the proposed communication enhancement program to the school administrators. • Conference with the heads and communication instructors about the communicative competence status as well as the communication enhancement program. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write a letter requesting meeting for meeting with the school administrators. • Presentation of the proposed communication enhancement program. • Sorting and delegating of roles and responsibilities in the implementation of the program. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To initiate dialogue for improved school dynamics. • To articulate strategy for efficient communication. • To streamline implementation through clear assignments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School administrators • Program Heads • English Language and Communication Instructors • Researcher 	None	Written letter and program of activities
Phase II: During Intervention Phase						
Week 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Program Introduction and Expectations <p>Module 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mastering Transitional Flow in Writing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on communicative competence and its importance. • Acknowledging and recognizing expectations of the participants. • Reiterating the goal and objectives of the program. • Interactive discussion and workshop training on how to master transitional flow in writing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To clearly outline the program's purpose and scope to stakeholders, fostering understanding and engagement from the outset. • To establish clear expectations for participants, ensuring alignment with program goals and promoting accountability throughout its duration. • To enhance coherence for better understanding. • To foster smooth reading experience with seamless transitions. • To strengthen arguments through logical connectivity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School administrators • Program Heads • Instructors • Researchers • Keynote speaker 	5,000.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendance form • Certificate • Worksheet • Photo Documents
Week 3	<p>Module 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing Interpretation of Non-Verbal Cues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input from the expert • Role-play scenarios: Participants interpret non-verbal cues in scripted interactions. • Observation exercises: Identify and interpret non-verbal cues in video clips. • Interactive games: Guess emotions based on non-verbal cues displayed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To improve accuracy in decoding non-verbal cues. • To enhance understanding of body language subtleties. • To strengthen communication skills through non-verbal interpretation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School administrators • Program Heads • Instructors • Researchers • Keynote speaker (Communication Expert) 	5,000.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendance form • Certificate • Worksheet • Photo Documents
Week 4	<p>Module 3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapting Language Formality for Effective Communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input from the speaker • Role-play scenarios: Participants adapt language formality in various professional contexts. • Group discussions: Analyze language formality in real-world communication examples. • Writing exercises: Rewrite informal texts into appropriate formal language. • Presentation evaluations: Provide feedback on language formality in peers' presentations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To anchor language formality for diverse communication contexts. • To enhance professionalism through adaptable language usage. • To improve rapport by matching language formality to audience. • To foster clarity and respect through appropriate language adaptation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School administrators • Program Heads • Instructors • Researchers • Keynote speaker (Communication Expert) 	5,000.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendance form • Certificate • Worksheet • Photo Documents
Week 5	<p>Module 4:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building Trust and Rapport through Effective Communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive inputting from the speaker. • Role-play exercises: Participants practice active listening and empathy. • Trust-building games: Engage in activities promoting cooperation and teamwork. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To foster trust through active listening and empathetic communication • To strengthen rapport via transparent and respectful interactions. • To cultivate teamwork by encouraging open 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School administrators • Program Heads • Instructors • Researchers • Keynote speaker (Communication Expert) 	5,000.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendance form • Certificate • Worksheet • Photo Documents

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feedback sessions: Provide constructive feedback on communication behaviors. Group discussions: Explore trust-building strategies and share personal experiences. 	<p>dialogue and collaboration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enhance relationships through consistent and reliable communication practices. 			
Week 6	<p>Module 5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addressing Misunderstandings and Assertive Communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive discussion from the expert Role-play scenarios: Participants practice assertive communication to resolve misunderstandings. Case studies: Analyze real-life examples and propose assertive communication strategies. Mock negotiations: Simulate conflict resolution scenarios to practice assertiveness. Feedback circles: Provide constructive feedback on communication effectiveness in resolving conflicts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To clarify misconceptions assertively for mutual understanding. To build confidence in expressing needs and boundaries assertively. To resolve conflicts promptly through clear and respectful communication. To foster trust and respect by addressing misunderstandings openly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> School administrators Program Heads Instructors Researchers Keynote speaker (Communication Expert) 	5,000.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendance form Certificate Worksheet Photo Documents
Phase III: Post- Intervention Phase						
Week 7	Monitoring and Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Post-Program Assessment Feedbacking and Recommendations Recognition Ceremony 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To evaluate program effectiveness to inform future improvements. To measure participant satisfaction and learning outcomes for program evaluation. To gather feedback for continuous program enhancement and refinement. To provide actionable recommendations based on participant input and observations. To celebrate participants' achievements and contributions to the program. To acknowledge and honor individuals for their dedication and excellence. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> School administrators Program Heads Instructors Researchers Keynote speaker (Communication Expert) 	10,000.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendance form Certificate Worksheet Photo Documents
					Total Amount:	35,000.00

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to determine the level of communicative competence among its four major components; grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, and strategic competence of 1st year tertiary learners of Christ the King College-Gingoog City. This study also identified the extent of students' perception about the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching in enhancing their ability to communicate in real-world situations.

It utilized a descriptive-correlational type of research and made use of a self-made questionnaire in determining the level of competence among the four major components of communicative competence as well as on identifying the extent of TBLT's effectiveness in enhancing ability to communicate in real world. The study hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between the communicative competence of participants and their perception on the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). There were 150 participants in the conduct of this study and were chosen using a stratified random sampling.

The findings of the study revealed that the demographic profile of the participants in terms of associated program/courses the highest number of representations came from the Social Work Program.

In terms of the level of communicative competence across its four major components, sociolinguistic competence got the highest overall weighted mean of 3.77. Second to the highest is grammatical competence which have an overall weighted mean of 3.56. Following which is the discourse competence with an overall weighted mean of 3.50. On the other hand, it turned out that strategic competence got the lowest overall weighted mean of 2.96. Though each of these components have a differing weighted mean, it can be noted that the students in general have a neutral stance on the indicators of communicative competence, thus implying a moderate level of communicative competence.

The analysis of the data revealed that the learners have high perception on Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) effectiveness in enhancing communication in real-world situation. This indicated the capacity of Task-Based Language Teaching to support the development of communication through authentic and immersive practices. On the other hand, among all the four components of communicative competence, only sociolinguistic competence yielded significant relationship with the perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) with $p = 0.039$.

As a result of the data gathered, an innovative communication enhancement program, which bears the acronym NONCHALANT: Nurturing Optimal Networking for Communication Habits and Language Techniques was proposed.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The Social Work program has the highest representation among participants, followed by Accountancy, Criminal Justice, Hospitality and Management, Information

and Technology, and Teacher Education programs. Meanwhile, the Business Administration program has the lowest representation.

Relative to the extent of the participants' communicative competence, they have high level of proficiency in sociolinguistic competence, grammar competence, and discourse competence. Meanwhile, the participants have a moderate level of proficiency on strategic competence. Altogether, the communicative competence of the learners is at moderate level.

The extent of tertiary learners' perception on the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching in enhancing communication in real-world situation is high.

Moreover, there is a moderate positive correlation between participants' grammatical competence and their perceived effectiveness of TBLT. While stronger grammatical foundations tend to result in a more favourable view of TBLT, this correlation is not statistically significant, suggesting chance may influence the relationship.

There is weak positive correlation exists between participants' perceived effectiveness of TBLT and their sociolinguistic competence. The correlation is statistically significant; indicating a tendency for tertiary learners finding TBLT beneficial to also demonstrate slightly better sociolinguistic skills.

Furthermore, there is a weak positive correlation exist between participants' perceived effectiveness of TBLT and their discourse competence. While these correlations suggest a slight tendency for those finding TBLT beneficial to demonstrate somewhat stronger discourse skills, the lack of statistical significance indicates chance may play a role in the observed relationships.

There is weak positive correlation between students' perceived effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and their strategic competence. This suggests a slight tendency for students who perceive TBLT as more beneficial to also exhibit somewhat stronger skills in sustaining and maintaining communication.

An innovative communication enhancement program bearing the acronym NONCHALANT: Nurturing Optimal Networking for Communication Habits and Language Techniques, with outlined components, topics and activities was developed.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are drawn:

1. Teachers may be recommended to attend training-workshops and other professional development programs related to Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)- informed pedagogies.

2. School administrators may initiate the conduct of trainings and seminars about communication enhancement in a school-wide basis.

3. Curriculum experts may be encouraged to regularly update the effectiveness of existing syllabus on communication subjects and programs and design it based on trajectories of English Language Teaching.

4. Higher education institutions (HEIs) may adopt the proposed innovative communication program tailored to enhance the communicative competence of the tertiary learners.

5. Educational researchers may undergo deeper investigation to validate the result of this study. Moreover, grammatical and discourse competence may also be revisited as focal areas of investigation.

6. Future researchers may replicate this study about communicative competence and Task-Based Language Teaching and venture on integrating additional scope, datasets, and context.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to the principles of voluntary participation where respondents are given discretion to withdraw participation in the study anytime as deemed necessary. An informed consent which includes outline of the study's goal, direction and purpose was also secured from the respondents. The researchers also adhered with utmost diligence on the principle of beneficence; where maximum benefits were acquired negating any possible risk or harm of any kind from the participants.

The data privacy, meaning that the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents was vouched to be protected at all times as well as conditions that the respondents will not be subjected to any acts of deception or betrayal in this research process or its published outcomes. Participants were also informed that they have the right to know the conclusion of this study.

Likewise, the researcher understands what plagiarism entails and is aware of the school's policy in this regard. The researcher undertakes not to make use of another person's previous work without acknowledgement or to submit it as his/her own

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